

SELF-REGULATION AND SELF-PERCEIVED COMPETENCE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS

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Self-Regulation and Self-Perceived Competence of High School Students in Relation to Academic Performance in Mathematics

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of self-regulation and self-perceived competence of high school students in relation to academic performance in mathematics. The subject and respondents of the study were the junior high school students who were officially enrolled at Francisco Infante Memorial High School for the school year 2022-23. The researcher utilized the descriptive method of research. Valid and reliable questionnaires were used as the data gathering instruments which were patterned from The Self-Regulation Formative Questionnaire, which measured a student's perceived level of proficiency in the four essential components of self-regulation (Gaumer & Noonan, 2018), and Children's Perceived Competence Scale. The data gathered were processed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The results showed that the students exhibit a moderate self-perceived competence as a whole and in terms of cognitive, social, physical, and self-growth. They also have a high degree of self-regulation when taken as a whole and in the areas of plan, monitor, control, and reflect. The level of high school pupils' academic achievement in mathematics is very satisfactory. Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between the level of self-regulation and the level of academic performance in mathematics. In addition, there is a significant relationship between the level of self-perceived competence and the level of academic performance in mathematics. Moreover, the level of self-perceived competence and the level of academic performance in mathematics are correlated with each other.

Keywords: *self-regulation, self-perceived competence, academic performance, students*

Introduction

Competency-based education is being implemented at deeper levels in more schools every year. It is a major shift in school culture, structures, and pedagogy focused on ensuring that all students succeed and addressing the fundamental shortcomings of the traditional model (Levine, Patrick, 2019). It puts forth the theory that the majority of students will achieve competence in the specified content area as long as they are given the opportunity and freedom to progress at their own pace and their learning experiences are structured according to their interests and needs (Sturgis and Casey, 2018 as cited in Levine & Patrick, 2019). Competency-based education is being integrated into more and more schools every year. School culture, structures, and pedagogy will change fundamentally as a result of this change to ensure all students can succeed, regardless of whether they decide to attend college or pursue a career (skilled) pathway. The focus should be on proficiency-based practices, such as putting a high priority on knowledge and skills, providing quality learning experiences aligned to clear outcomes, and guaranteeing that all students have access to support to reach the proficiency standards. For schools to see real benefits for students, families, and teachers alike, they must be better equipped, learn, and identify quality design principles (Cuyacot & Cuyacot, 2022).

On the other hand, self-regulation describes a number of conscious and unconscious mechanisms that the human brain uses to exert control over the way the body and its internal systems function. The main mechanism by which the self affects the organism is self-regulation (Nodeh, 2021). However, it has been established and underlined how self-perceived affects students' learning and attainment of academic objectives that high self-perceived students have faith in their capacity to understand a lesson, work through problems in the classroom, and finish a task. On the other hand, the evaluation of self-perceived competence offers benefits since it reveals the student's drive to preserve and develop the skills in issue, which is presented as one component in the idea of self-efficacy especially in Mathematics field (Hayat et al., 2020).

Furthermore, self-regulated learning interventions improve student's academic performance and self-regulation skills across subjects, including Mathematics. These interventions, particularly those based on metacognition theories and targeting multiple strategies, have been found effective in enhancing math achievement (Wang & Sperling, 2020). In the study of Costa et al. (2019) the research emphasizes the importance of developing a relationship between perceived self-regulation and self-perceived competence as factors that influence this process because learning for humans is a dynamic and complex process. Additionally, this is crucial for increasing motivation for learning because students who believe they are competent tend to persevere longer in carrying out activities correctly.

Lastly, in the Philippines the implications of self-regulation and self-perceived ability of students' learning and attainment of academic goals have been highlighted which is challenging among high school students. Academic goal is a major challenge for high school students since students with high self-efficacy believe that they can understand their lessons easily, overcome educational challenges, and complete a task efficiently. High self-efficacy students have the conviction that they can comprehend a lesson, work out academic challenges, and finish an assignment. In contrast to students who have low self-efficacy, they think they can comprehend and solve mathematical issues. With this, researcher aims find out the level of self-regulation and self-perceived competence of high school

students in relation to their academic performance in mathematics. In line with this, the study is being investigated.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of self-regulation and self-perceived competence among high school students in relation with their academic performance in mathematics. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of self-regulation of high school students when taken as a whole and when classified in terms of:
 - 1.1. plan;
 - 1.2. monitor;
 - 1.3. control; and
 - 1.4. reflect?
2. What is the level of self-perceived competence of high students when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive;
 - 2.2. social;
 - 2.3. physical; and
 - 2.4. general self-worth?
3. What is the level of academic performance of high school students in mathematics?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of their self-regulation and the level of academic performance of high school students in mathematics?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of self-perceived competence and the level of academic performance of high students in mathematics?

Literature Review

According to Hakiki and Qolby's (2019) study, indicating that students' self-regulated learning abilities play a pivotal role in time management through effective planning, direction, and feedback utilization, thereby contributing to enhanced academic performance.

Results of the study of Mamolo & Sugano (2020) indicate that the overall self-perceived competency was satisfactory ($M = 2.73$, $SD = 0.66$). The study of Venkatesan & Shankar (2022) indicates that there exists a substantial beneficial relationship between perceived competence and academic performance. Several aspects have been identified as determining student retention in higher education, including academic and social integration, cognitive capability, motivation, individual circumstances. Time management, learning abilities, self-monitoring, technology competence, and research skills were all consistent academic qualities for higher education courses (Mah & Ifenthaler, 2017). Study revealed that adolescents with strong control, social isolation, loss of privileges, problem solving, emotional management, stress capacity to deal, and general psychosocial competence were shown to have higher levels of perceived competence. The findings of the study demonstrate the importance of perceived reality, self-efficacy and decision-making process in the development of life skills students who express high protectiveness, obedience, reward, critical thinking, self-awareness, self-beliefs interpersonal interaction and effective communication.

The study of Landicho (2021) which indicates that students exhibit eagerness to learn the subject and attain good grades. Students' interest in mathematics plays a crucial role in acquiring mathematical skills and knowledge, making it a pivotal factor for achieving academic excellence in mathematics. The study further suggests that students' interest in learning positively influences academic performance, providing insights into the role of academic interest across disciplines. A research study conducted by Callaman & Itas (2020) suggests a positive correlation, indicating that students with enhanced numerical skills tend to achieve higher success in mathematics overall.

However, Sahranavard et al.'s (2018) findings suggested a strong connection between self-regulation components and educational performance components. Students employing increased self-regulating strategies demonstrate success not only in future planning but also in cultivating self-efficacy. Enhanced cognitive self-regulation among students correlates with improved academic performance, facilitated by effective emotional management and resistance to emotional influences. Additionally, students exhibiting superior self-regulation skills display heightened motivation for learning and are adept at formulating targeted plans.

The research of Mamolo and Sogano's (2020) indicate that students tend to perceive their competence at a higher level than their actual academic proficiency. This suggests that the students' real academic performance in general mathematics is typically lower than their self-perceived competence. This observation aligns with the assertion that an increased perception of academic competence can boost students' intrinsic motivation, consequently fostering academic achievement.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this study was descriptive research with a correlational design to explore the relationship between dependent and independent variables. According to Chaudhari (2021) descriptive research is used to collect information about the current state of phenomena and to depict what was present in terms of variables or conditions within a particular situation.

A descriptive study involves reporting summary data, encompassing measures of central tendency like mean, median, mode, deviance from the mean, variation, percentage, and Mann-Whitney. Descriptive research serves as an exploration of status and finds extensive application in education. Its significance lies in the belief that through observation, analysis, and description, problems can be solved, and practices can be enhanced.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the junior high school students who were officially enrolled at Francisco Infante Memorial High School, academic year 2022-2023.

Instrument

The researcher employed a standard questionnaire adapted from The Self-Regulation Formative Questionnaire. This instrument measured a student's perceived proficiency in the four essential components of self-regulation, as developed by Gaumer, E.A.S & Noonan in 2018. Additionally, self-perceived competence was assessed using the Children's Perceived Competence Scale by Nagai et al. (2015).

This study utilized a survey questionnaire consisting of two parts; Part I presented the level of self-regulation of high school students when taken as a whole and when classified in terms of plan, monitor, control, and reflect.

Part II of the questionnaire, which included three level of self-perceived competence of high students in terms of cognitive, social, physical, and general of self-worth. Part III presented the level of academic performance of high school students in Mathematics. The respondents rated each item using the following five-point scale with the corresponding verbal interpretations.

Procedure

The researcher sent a request letter to the school principal for the conduct of the study. After securing the approval, questionnaires were administered to the target respondents. They were sent to the respondents. The information collected from the respondents' responses was tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences).

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the study Self-Regulation and Self-Perceived Competence of High School Students in Relation to Academic Performance in Mathematics, ethical considerations were strictly observed to protect the rights and well-being of respondents. Informed consent from both students and their guardians were sought to ensure they understand the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks, with the option to withdraw at any time without consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained by securely handling data and ensuring that personal information remains undisclosed. Fairness and objectivity in data collection and analysis were observed to prevent bias, while responsible data management was practiced, including secure storage and proper disposal of sensitive information. Finally, obtaining ethical clearance from relevant school authorities or an ethics review board adhere to research standards, promoting integrity and safeguarding respondents throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Self-Regulation of High School Students

Table below presents the level of self-regulation of high school students when taken as a whole and when classified in terms of plan, monitor, control, and reflect

Table 2. Level of Self-Regulation of High School Students

<i>Self-Regulation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Plan	3.45	High
Monitor	3.42	High
Control	3.41	High
Reflect	3.46	High
As a whole	3.44	High

Based on Table 2, the level of self-regulation of high school students in terms of plan, monitor, control, and reflect has a high level with a mean of 3.45, 3.42, 3.41, and 3.46, respectively. As a whole, the level of self-regulation of the high school students, with a mean of 3.44, is interpreted as high.

This implies that high school students possess a commendably high degree of self-regulation, showcasing proficiency in planning, monitoring, controlling, and reflecting on their academic activities. They have a high ability to understand and manage behavior and reactions to feelings.

The results align with Hakiki and Qolby's (2019) study, indicating that students' self-regulated learning abilities play a pivotal role in time management through effective planning, direction, and feedback utilization, thereby contributing to enhanced academic performance.

Level of Self-Perceived Competence of High Students

Table below shows the level of self-perceived competence of high school students when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of cognitive, social, physical, and general self-worth.

Table 3. Level of Self-Perceived Competence of High School Students

<i>Self-Perceived Competence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Cognitive	3.03	Moderate
Social	3.13	Moderate
Physical	3.02	Moderate
General Self-Worth	3.31	Moderate
As a whole	3.12	Moderate

The table shows that the level of self-perceived competence of high school students in terms of cognitive, social, physical, and self-growth has a moderate level with a mean of 3.03, 3.13, 3.02, and 3.31, respectively. As a whole, the level of self-perceived competence of the high school students is moderate, with a mean of 3.12. This implies that high school students generally perceive themselves moderately across cognitive, social, physical, and self-growth domains, indicating a balanced self-assessment encompassing various aspects of their development. They have a moderate belief on their abilities and performance.

The findings are in accordance with results of the study of Mamolo & Sugano (2020) which indicate that the overall self-perceived competency of students in mathematics was satisfactory ($M = 2.73$, $SD = 0.66$).

The study of Venkatesan & Shankar (2022) also indicates that there exists a substantial beneficial relationship between perceived competence and academic performance. Several aspects have been identified as determining student retention in higher education, including academic and social integration, cognitive capability, motivation, individual circumstances. Time management, learning abilities, self-monitoring, technology competence, and research skills were all consistent academic qualities for higher education courses (Mah & Ifenthaler, 2017). Study revealed that adolescents with strong control, social isolation, loss of privileges, problem solving, emotional management, stress capacity to deal, and general psychosocial competence were shown to have higher levels of perceived competence. The findings of the study demonstrate the importance of perceived reality, self-efficacy and decision-making process in the development of life skills students who express high protectiveness, obedience, reward, critical thinking, self-awareness, self-beliefs interpersonal interaction and effective communication.

Level of Academic Performance of High School Students in Mathematics

The table on the next page presents the level of academic performance of high school students in mathematics.

Table 4. Level of Academic Performance of High School Students in Mathematics

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	48	87.17	Very Satisfactory
Very Satisfactory	74		
Satisfactory	39		
Fairly Satisfactory	5		
Did Not Meet Expectation	0		
Total	166		

The table highlights those 78 respondents achieved a very satisfactory level of academic performance, 48 demonstrated an outstanding level, 39 respondents attained a satisfactory level, and five respondents achieved a fairly satisfactory level.

Overall, the overall academic performance of high school students in mathematics is very satisfactory, yielding a mean of 87.17. This implies that majority of high school students excel in mathematics, showcasing a positive overall academic performance and suggesting a strong foundation in the subject. They are striving to perform and comply the requirements of the subject and try to excel inspite of the difficulty of the topics.

The results align with the study of Landicho (2021) which indicates that students exhibit eagerness to learn the subject and attain good grades. Students' interest in mathematics plays a crucial role in acquiring mathematical skills and knowledge, making it a pivotal factor for achieving academic excellence in mathematics. The study further suggests that students' interest in learning positively influences academic performance, providing insights into the role of academic interest across disciplines. A research study conducted by Callaman & Itaas (2020) suggests a positive correlation, indicating that students with enhanced numerical skills tend to achieve higher success in mathematics overall.

Relationship Between the Level of Self-Regulation and the Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics

The table below presents the relationship between the level of self-regulation and the level of academic performance of high school students in mathematics.

Table 5. Relationship Between the Level of Self-Regulation and the Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics

Level of Self-Regulation	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	1	5	2	0	0	8
High	30	26	12	1	0	69
Moderate	15	43	23	3	0	84
Low	2	0	2	1	0	5
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	48	74	39	5	0	166

Computed Value: 0.309

P-value: 0.006

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 5% level of Significance

The table above shows that out of 166 respondents, 84 of them have a moderate level of self-regulation, 43 have a very satisfactory level of academic performance, and three of them possess a fairly satisfactory level. Moreover, five of the respondents have a low level of self-regulation; two have an outstanding level of academic performance, another two possess a satisfactory level, and only one has a fairly satisfactory level.

Using Goodman-Kruskal's gamma, it reveals that the computed value obtained is 0.309, while the p-value is 0.006, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant correlation between the degree of self-regulation and the level of academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the level of self-regulation significantly influences the level of academic performance.

The results conform to Sahranavard et al.'s (2018) findings which suggested a strong connection between self-regulation components and educational performance components. Students employing increased self-regulating strategies demonstrate success not only in future planning but also in cultivating self-efficacy.

Enhanced cognitive self-regulation among students correlates with improved academic performance, facilitated by effective emotional management and resistance to emotional influences. Additionally, students exhibiting superior self-regulation skills display heightened motivation for learning and are adept at formulating targeted plans.

Relationship Between the Level of Self-Perceived Competence and the Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics

The table presents the relationship between the level of self-perceived competence and the level of academic performance of high school students in mathematics.

Table 6. Relationship Between the Level of Self-Perceived Competence and the Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics

Level of Self-Perceived competence	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	0	1	1	0	0	2
High	6	17	11	2	0	36
Moderate	36	50	26	2	0	144
Low	6	6	1	1	0	14
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	48	74	39	5	0	166

Computed Value: -0.304

P-value: 0.012

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 5% level of Significance

The table shows that 144 out of 166 respondents possess a moderate level of self-perceived competence, 50 of them have a very satisfactory level, and two have a fairly satisfactory level of academic performance. Moreover, only two have a very high level of self-perceived competence, with one having a very satisfactory level and the other having a satisfactory level of academic performance.

Using Goodman-Kruskal's gamma, it reveals that the computed value obtained is -0.304, while the p-value is 0.012, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the level of self-perceived competence and the level of academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the level of self-perceived competence significantly impacts the academic performance in mathematics of the high school students.

The finding is in consonance with Mamolo and Sogano's (2020) research, indicating that students tend to perceive their competence at a higher level than their actual academic proficiency. This suggests that the students' real academic performance in general mathematics is typically lower than their self-perceived competence. This observation aligns with the assertion that an increased perception of academic competence can boost students' intrinsic motivation, consequently fostering academic achievement.

Conclusions

Based on the findings above, the researcher therefore concludes that:

High school students have a high level of ability to understand and manage behavior and reactions to feelings.

High school students have a moderate self-perceived competence in the areas of cognitive, social, physical, and self-growth, showing a moderate belief in their abilities and performance.

The high school pupils' academic achievement in mathematics is highly acceptable.

The level of self-regulation influences the level of academic performance.

The level of self-perceived competence and the academic performance level in mathematics are correlated with each other.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

More seminars/workshops focusing on passion and commitment towards long-term goals for teachers since it is the predominant factor that provides the energy for going on, against challenges and setbacks of being an educator.

School administrators should ensure an authentic and positive environment within the workplace.

Teachers may do their tasks, responsibilities and what are expected from them in order to achieve their goals and never give up even in the face of adversity or challenges.

Specific strategies may be developed to work on a more immediate impulse control and perseverance and passion for studying more.

School administrators and the DepEd as a whole may come up with a program to re-awaken the passion, perseverance and commitment of teachers to their work for them to choose to stay and teach Filipino children rather than choose to teach abroad.

The school can establish new routine where older teachers will not feel burned-out towards their job.

Future researchers can conduct similar research in another locale and may include factors affecting the self-regulation and self-perceived competence of high school students.

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